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PROGRAMA DACIU

**Integrability and entanglement in
quantum systems**

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Introduction

DACIU is an excellence program created by Fundación Avanza, whose objective is introducing undergraduate students to scientific research. This task is carried out via a one-year project where the student, with the help of a supervisor, gets a deeper insight into a specific topic (proposed by the latter), which is usually outside the University curriculum.

The purpose of this document is to gather all the work the author did as a participant of this program. The project was performed under the supervision of Artemio González López¹ and it focused on the study of integrability and entanglement in low-dimensional quantum systems.

The first chapter of the document is devoted to the study of integrability. After a brief review of this concept, it studies the Calogero model, a well known integrable system of one dimension. Its main properties and alternative versions of the model (scalar and spin Calogero model, and Polychronakos-Frahm model) are explored here. To finish this section, a method called 'Freezing Trick' is given as a way to compute the partition function of the Polychronakos-Frahm chain.

The second part of the document addresses the topic of quantum entanglement. It introduces the notion of entanglement entropy as a way to quantify the lack of information caused by this phenomenon. Then, these concepts are applied to the study of the Heisenberg XX model. Particularly, it presents an explicit computation of the entanglement entropy of a block of the chain when the system is in the ground state. Finally, some possible generalizations of the model, which conserve its translational invariance, are discussed, leaving opened the possibility for studying similar systems with a different type of interaction between particles.

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INTEGRABILITY

Introduction to the Calogero model

The reasons that lead a physicist to study a particular model usually fit into one of two big categories. First, one may choose to work in a model based on its applicability, motivated by its potential to appear in many different situations or to perfectly describe a specific phenomenon. On the other hand, sometimes it is just the intrinsic beauty of the problem the only motivation one needs. The possibility to find an elegant and exact solution to a certain problem is very uncommon in the study of physics, and the opportunity to do so might be enough to justify the effort. As one could expect, the models that fit into the intersection of these two divisions are extremely rare, but the Calogero model² happens to be one of them. This system, which consists of one-dimensional particles with inverse-square pairwise interactions, is not only the great example for an integrable and solvable many-body system, but it appears in a wide and diverse range of situations: condensed matter physics, fluid mechanics, spin chains, string theory... Moreover, both its classical and quantum version are worth studying. In this document, we will mainly focus on the quantum case, however, a brief introduction to the classical model will also be discussed.

Description of the model

The Hamiltonian of the basic Calogero model is given by

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{2} p_i^2 + \sum_{i<j} \frac{g}{(x_i - x_j)^2}, \quad (1)$$

where g denotes the coupling constant and we have scaled the mass of the particles to unity. This model exhibits some special features caused by the particular shape of the potential. This inverse-square interaction is unique as it sits in the borderline between opposite behaviors in many different contexts. In higher dimensions, this type of potential arises as a centrifugal term: anything weaker than that at short distances would imply that particles cannot get too close, while if a stronger interaction

²Sometimes, it receives names as Calogero-Moser model, Calogero-Sutherland model... but we shall simply call it Calogero model for brevity, referring to its original creator.

appeared when the particles are close to each other, they would inevitably fall into each other. If we analyze now this potential in the context of long-distance interaction, it is also the frontier for statistical mechanics phase transitions, as any stronger potential leads to phase transitions, while a weaker one does not. Finally, in the context of the quantum model, the potential scales like the kinetic term and hence the constant g is dimensionless (taking $\hbar = 1$).

Classically, this system is stable (the particles do not collapse into each other) for positive values of g , which simply means that the force between the particle is repulsive. However, in Quantum Mechanics we have to make use of the uncertainty principle, and a value of g greater than $-\frac{1}{4}$ is enough to ensure that the particles do not collapse into each other ([1]).

For later convenience, we shall express this parameter as $g = a(a - 1)$ (in the classical motion it will simply be $g = a^2$). Then, from the previous considerations it follows that the minimum value for a is $\frac{1}{2}$.³

Integrability and classical motion

In a N classical particles Hamiltonian system, where the i th particle position is given by q_i and its momentum by p_i , we can define the Poisson bracket of two functions of the motion (i.e., quantities that depend on $(q_1, \dots, q_N, p_1, \dots, p_N, t)$) f and g to be:

$$\{f, g\} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial f}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial q_i} \right).$$

From Hamilton's equation, it is easy to check that the evolution of any function of the motion is given by its Poisson bracket with the Hamiltonian:

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial q_i} \frac{dq_i}{dt} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial p_i} \frac{dp_i}{dt} \right) = \{f, H\}.$$

This means that any quantity with vanishing Poisson bracket with the Hamiltonian must be conserved during the motion. This type of functions are called first integral of motions.

Now, we can define a system to be *integrable* if it has N independent integral of motions that are in involution, i.e., the Poisson bracket of any two of them is equal to zero. For this kind of system, we can apply the Liouville–Arnold theorem that tell us that the phase space of the system is diffeomorphic to a N -dimensional torus where we can introduce the so called *action – angle* variables that allow us to solve the equation of motion of the system by quadratures (see [2] for more information).

If we come back to the Calogero model, one way we can prove that it is indeed

³Here, we assume that $a > 0$. Otherwise, it could be changed by $1 - a$ and the resulting potential would be the same.

an integrable system is using the method of the Lax's pair (see[3] for a better explanation of this method). If we define the following matrices

$$L_{jk} = p_j \delta_{jk} + (1 - \delta_{jk}) \frac{ia}{x_{jk}}, \quad M_{jk} = a \delta_{jk} \sum_{l=1}^N \frac{1}{x_{jl}^2} + a(\delta_{jk} - 1) \frac{1}{x_{jk}^2},$$

with $g = a^2$, then we can deduce after applying the equations of motion, that the evolution of the matrix L can be expressed as:

$$\dot{L} = i[L, M].$$

With this information, we can prove that the eigenvalues of L are conserved during the motion. First, we see that L is an hermitian matrix, so it must exist an orthonormal basis $\{v_n\}$ such that $Lv_n = \lambda_n v_n$ and $\lambda_n \in \mathbb{R}, \forall n$. Then, if we denote by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ the dot product in \mathbb{C}^N , we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_n &= \langle v_n, Lv_n \rangle \\ \Rightarrow \dot{\lambda}_n &= \langle v_n, \dot{L}v_n \rangle + \langle \dot{v}_n, Lv_n \rangle + \langle Lv_n, \dot{v}_n \rangle \\ &= \langle Lv_n, Mv_n \rangle - \langle v_n, MLv_n \rangle + \lambda_n (\langle \dot{v}_n, v_n \rangle + \langle v_n, \dot{v}_n \rangle) \\ &= i \langle v_n, Mv_n \rangle (\lambda_n - \lambda_n) + \lambda_n \frac{d}{dt} \langle v_n, v_n \rangle = 0, \end{aligned}$$

and the eigenvalues of the matrix L are conserved during the motion.

Actually, as the eigenvalues of the matrix L do not change during the motion, the following traces

$$I_n = \text{tr}(L^n), \quad n = 1, \dots, N,$$

are constants of motion. Now we need to check that they are in involution. To do so, we take the limit $t \rightarrow \infty$ where the off-diagonal elements of the matrix L vanish as the particles fly away from each other. Then $L = \text{diag}(k_i)$, where k_i is the asymptotic momentum of the i th particle ($k_i = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} p_i$) and the constants of motion are simply $I_n = \sum_i k_i^n$. These values are obviously in involution (their Poisson bracket is zero), and hence, as the Poisson bracket of two conserved magnitudes is conserved, it must also vanish for all t . Actually, it is clear that $I_1 = \sum_n p_n$ is the total momentum of the system, while it can be shown that $I_2 = 2H$. The first integrals $I_n, n \geq 3$, generate other non trivial conserved quantities.

We have just proved that the model is integrable. Apart from that, another really interesting property of the classical Calogero model (that will also occur in its quantum analogue) is that it closely resembles a free particles system. As the force between particles is always repulsive, they tend to get further away from each other as $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$, causing the interaction between them to drop to zero. Therefore, in this limit, we will have that the equation of motion of the n th particle will be indeed the one of a free particle:

$$x_n(t) = p_n^\pm \cdot t + x_n^\pm + o(1) \text{ when } t \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2)$$

In addition, due to the singularity of the (repulsive) potential when the distance between particles is zero, the particles must remain in the same order during the

motion. Therefore, it makes sense to label them following that order, so that

$$x_n < x_{n+1}, \quad n = 1, \dots, N-1.$$

If we combine these conditions with (2), it must be

$$p_n^- > p_{n+1}^-, \quad p_n^+ < p_{n+1}^+, \quad n = 1, \dots, N-1. \quad (3)$$

Now, if we are given a set of values $\{p_n^-\}$ that satisfy (3) we can solve the scattering problem with the help of the Lax pair formulation. We have seen that in the asymptotic limit $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$, L becomes diagonal. Therefore, the set of eigenvalues $\{p_n^\pm\}$ must be equal to $\{\lambda_n\}$ when $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$, but these quantities are time-independent. Then, it must be $\{p_n^+\} = \{p_n^-\}$. If we now make use of the restrictions from (3), it needs to be

$$p_n^+ = p_{N+1-n}^-, \quad n = 1, \dots, N.$$

In conclusion, the classical motion of the basic Calogero model is very peculiar. In the far past, the particles behaved like free particles. Then, they come close to each other and interact, however, this interaction can be viewed as a ‘‘particle shuffle’’, from where the particles come out and tend to follow the path that another particle would have had if there were no interaction.

The quantum system

The properties of the classical motion, and in particular the integrability, are shared with the quantum system ([1]). In this case, we will also introduce a quadratic term in the potential. This way, we will have a confined system whose Hamiltonian is

$$H^{sc} = - \sum_i \partial_{x_i}^2 + a^2 \sum_i x_i^2 + a \sum_{i \neq j} \frac{a-1}{(x_i - x_j)^2}. \quad (4)$$

We will refer to this model as scalar Calogero model, as its particles have no spin. This model’s behavior is similar to the classical one, it resembles the motion of the system without the inverse-quadratic pairwise interaction. Actually, as it is shown in [4], its energy spectrum is

$$E_{\mathbf{n}}^{sc} = E_0 + 2a \sum_i n_i, \quad E_0 \equiv aN(a(N-1) + 1), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{n} = (n_1, \dots, n_N)$, with $n_1 \geq \dots \geq n_N \geq 0$, which is the same as the usual N particle harmonic oscillator but with an energy shift.

If we now consider particles with spin, we can introduce the following Hamiltonian:

$$H = - \sum_i \partial_{x_i}^2 + a^2 \sum_i x_i^2 + a \sum_{i \neq j} \frac{a + S_{ij}}{(x_i - x_j)^2}, \quad (6)$$

where S_{ij} is the operator that permutes the spin state of the i th and j th particles. This model has the same energy spectrum as the scalar system ([5]).

The Polyrhonakos-Frahm spin chain and the freezing trick

In this section we will study the Polyrhonakos-Frahm spin chain, whose Hamiltonian is given by

$$H_{PF} = \sum_{i < j} \frac{1 + S_{ij}}{(\xi_i - \xi_j)^2}, \quad (7)$$

where $\{\xi_i\}$ are the equilibrium positions for the scalar potential of the spin Calogero model. Our objective will be to compute its partition function. To do so, we will make use of the “freezing trick” method (see [6]), which consists of taking the limit $a \rightarrow \infty$ in the spin and scalar Calogero model, so that the particles remain “frozen” in their equilibrium position and we can relate these three Hamiltonians ((4),(6) and (7)). However, to perform this process we need some previous results about these equilibrium positions.

The equilibrium positions of the scalar potential

The critical points of the scalar potential of the spin Calogero model must satisfy the following system of equations:

$$x_i = 2 \sum_{j, j \neq i} \frac{1}{(x_i - x_j)^3}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N.$$

In the appendix of this chapter, a proof is given that shows that the roots of the Hermite polynomial of N degree (which we will denote by $\{\xi_n\}$) do satisfy them. Therefore, we only need to prove that this critical point is unique and that they represent a minimum of the potential

$$V(x) = a^2 \sum_i x_i^2 + a^2 \sum_{i \neq j} \frac{1}{(x_i - x_j)^2}. \quad (8)$$

It is sufficient to prove this for the convex open set $A = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : x_1 < \dots < x_n\}$ since the ordering of the particles must remain constant during the motion due to the singularities of the potential (that are impenetrable even when quantum tunnelling is considered).

We start by proving that the Hessian matrix of the potential is positive definite. We first have that

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial x_i}(x) = 2a^2 x_i - 4a^2 \sum_{j, j \neq i} \frac{1}{(x_i - x_j)^3}.$$

Therefore, it must be

$$\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x_i^2}(x) = 2a^2 + 12a^2 \sum_{j, j \neq i} \frac{1}{(x_i - x_j)^4}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}(x) \stackrel{i \neq j}{=} -12a^2 \frac{1}{(x_i - x_j)^4}.$$

Then, if we have a vector $h \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $h \neq 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i,j} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}(x) h_{ij} &= 2a^2 \sum_i h_i^2 + 12a^2 \sum_{j,j \neq i} \frac{h_i^2}{(x_i - x_j)^4} - 12a^2 \sum_{j,j \neq i} \frac{h_i h_j}{(x_i - x_j)^4} \\ &= 2a^2 \|h\|^2 + 6a^2 \sum_{j,j \neq i} \frac{h_i^2 + h_j^2}{(x_i - x_j)^4} - 12a^2 \sum_{j,j \neq i} \frac{h_i h_j}{(x_i - x_j)^4} \\ &= 2a^2 \|h\|^2 + 6a^2 \sum_{j,j \neq i} \frac{(h_i - h_j)^2}{(x_i - x_j)^4} > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Now that we now that the Hessian matrix is positive definite everywhere in A , every critical point must be a minimum (we already knew that every minimum must be a critical point because A is open). Moreover, as we are working in a convex open set, this condition about the Hessian of V also means that the potential is a strictly convex function, i.e., for any $y_1, y_2 \in A$, we have that

$$V(ty_1 + (1-t)y_2) < tV(y_1) + (1-t)V(y_2), \quad 0 < t < 1.$$

Then, if we have two different minima $x, y \in A$, it must be

$$V(z) < V(x) = V(y), \quad \forall z \in \{tx + (1-t)y | 0 < t < 1\} \subset A,$$

which contradicts the fact that those points are minimum and leads to the conclusion that $x = y$ and we only have one (global) minimum.

The freezing trick

Now, we are ready to compute the partition function of (7). First, we observe that we can express the Hamiltonian of the spin Calogero model as follows:

$$H = H^{sc} + 2a H_{PF}|_{\xi_k \rightarrow x_k}. \quad (9)$$

With this relationship, we can apply the ‘‘freezing trick’’, which consists of taking the limit $a \rightarrow \infty$. In this situation, the scalar potential becomes the dominant part in (6), fixing⁴ the particles in their equilibrium positions $\{\xi_i\}$ (which we now that exist and are unique). As a consequence of this, in this limit the spatial and spin degrees of freedom are uncoupled and hence

$$\begin{aligned} H &\underset{a \rightarrow \infty}{=} H^{sc} + 2a H_{PF}, \\ E_{ij} &\underset{a \rightarrow \infty}{=} E_i^{sc} + 2a \mathcal{E}_j, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where E_{ij} and E_i^{sc} are the energies of the spin and scalar Calogero model, respectively, while \mathcal{E} is an eigenvalue of the Hamiltonian (7). Naively, one may think that this expression is enough to compute the spectrum of the PF chain once we know the energies of the Calogero model. However, we have no clue which value E_i^{sc} corresponds with \mathcal{E}_j to add up to E_{ij} , so it is useless to try to apply (10) this way. However, as we already know the values of the energies of the Calogero Model (they are given both in the scalar and the spin case by (5)), which are evenly spaced, we can deduce

⁴This means that the wave function of the system has a very narrow and high peak in the position $x_i = \xi_i$, and in the limit $a \rightarrow \infty$ it becomes a Dirac delta function with a pole in that specific value. This behavior is the same as the analogue classical system in equilibrium.

from (10) that so are the energies from the PF chain.

The correct way to use equation (10) is applying it to express the partition function of the spin chain (Z_{PF}) in terms of the partition functions of the spin and scalar Calogero model (which we will denote by Z and Z^{sc} , respectively):

$$\begin{aligned} Z(2aT) &= \sum_{\alpha} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\alpha}}{k_B 2aT}\right) \stackrel{a \rightarrow \infty}{=} \sum_{i,j} \exp\left(-\frac{E_i^{sc} + 2a\mathcal{E}_j}{k_B 2aT}\right) \\ &= \left(\sum_i \exp\left(-\frac{E_i^{sc}}{k_B 2aT}\right)\right) \cdot \left(\sum_j \exp\left(-\frac{\mathcal{E}_j^{sc}}{k_B T}\right)\right) = Z^{sc}(2aT) \cdot Z_{PF}(T) \\ &\Rightarrow Z_{PF}(T) = \lim_{a \rightarrow \infty} \frac{Z(2aT)}{Z^{sc}(2aT)}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where we have exploited in the first equality of the second line that the indexes of the summations are independent.

Now, our task is to compute the partition functions of each of the Calogero models. We shall start by the scalar version. First, we can subtract from H^{sc} the energy of the ground state E_0 (we will also remove it from H). Then, if we define $q = e^{-\frac{1}{k_B T}}$, the expression for the partition function of the model is

$$Z^{sc}(2aT) = \sum_{n_1 \geq \dots \geq n_N \geq 0} q^{\sum_{i=1}^N n_i}.$$

We see that evaluating the function at $2aT$ has removed the dependency on a , so it will not be necessary to study the limit $a \rightarrow \infty$.

A more compact and easy to manipulate expression can be obtained defining the values $p_j = n_j - n_{j+1}$ for $j = 1, \dots, N-1$, and $p_N = n_N$. It is easy to check that $\sum_{i=0}^N n_i = \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=i}^N p_j = \sum_{j=1}^N j p_j$, and hence

$$Z^{sc}(2aT) = \sum_{p_1, \dots, p_N \geq 0} q^{\sum_j j p_j} = \prod_{i=1}^N \left(\sum_{p_i=0}^{\infty} q^{i p_i} \right) = \prod_i (1 - q^i)^{-1}.$$

Once we know the partition function of the scalar model, we need to compute the value for $Z(2aT)$ now. The energies for this Hamiltonian are the same as before, as we have already mentioned. However, for this model we need to take into account the degeneracy caused by the particles' spin. In particular, if m is the number of internal degrees of freedom and

$$\mathbf{n} = (\overbrace{v_1, \dots, v_1}^{k_1}, \dots, \overbrace{v_r, \dots, v_r}^{k_r}), \quad v_1 > \dots > v_r \geq 0, \quad k_1 + \dots + k_r = N,$$

the degeneracy of the state is given by

$$d_{\mathbf{n}} = \prod_{i=1}^r \binom{m}{k_i} \equiv d(\mathbf{k}), \quad \mathbf{k} = (k_1, \dots, k_r).$$

To arrive at this expression we have used that if $n_i = n_j$ ($i \neq j$) it needs to be $s_i \neq s_j$ (so that the wave function does not vanish when it is antisymmetrized). Therefore,

the particles in the same sector v_i need to be in different spin states, and hence, $\binom{m}{k_i}$ counts how many possible ways there are to choose those k_i states we need from the m possible options.

Now we can compute the partition function of the system:

$$Z(2aT) = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{P}_N} \sum_{v_1 > \dots > v_r \geq 0} d(\mathbf{k}) q^{\sum_{i=1}^r k_i v_i},$$

where \mathcal{P}_N denotes the set of ordered partitions of N . Similarly as we did before, we can define $p_j = v_j - v_{j+1} > 0$, $j = 1, \dots, r-1$, and $p_r = v_r \geq 0$, hence:

$$\sum_{i=1}^r k_i v_i = \sum_{i=1}^r k_i \sum_{j=i}^r p_j = \sum_{j=1}^r K_j p_j,$$

where $K_j = \sum_{i=1}^j k_i$. Then, we can obtain the following expression for $Z(2aT)$:

$$\begin{aligned} Z(2aT) &= \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{P}_N} \prod_{i=1}^r \binom{m}{k_i} \sum_{p_1, \dots, p_{r-1} > 0} q^{\sum_{j=1}^{r-1} K_j p_j} \sum_{p_r \geq 0} q^{K_r p_r} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{P}_N} \prod_{i=1}^{r-1} \left(\binom{m}{k_i} \sum_{p_i=1}^{\infty} q^{K_i p_i} \right) \cdot \binom{m}{k_r} \sum_{p_r=0}^{\infty} q^{K_r p_r} = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{P}_N} q^{\sum_{i=1}^{r-1} K_i} \prod_{i=1}^r \binom{m}{k_i} (1 - q^{K_i})^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $1 \leq K_1 < \dots < K_{r-1} < K_r = N$, we can define $N - r$ natural numbers K'_i as

$$\{K'_1, \dots, K'_{N-r}\} = \{1, \dots, N-1\} - \{K_1, \dots, K_{r-1}\}.$$

Then, using the results we have for the values of $Z(2aT)$ and $Z^{sc}(2aT)$, we can finally obtain the expression for the partition function of the *PF* spin chain:

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{PF}(T) &\stackrel{a \rightarrow \infty}{=} \frac{Z(2aT)}{Z^{sc}(2aT)} = \frac{\sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{P}_N} q^{\sum_{i=1}^{r-1} K_i} \prod_{i=1}^r \binom{m}{k_i} (1 - q^{K_i})^{-1}}{\prod_i (1 - q^i)^{-1}} \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{P}_N} \prod_{i=1}^r \binom{m}{k_i} q^{\sum_{i=1}^{r-1} K_i} \prod_{i=1}^{N-r} (1 - q^{K'_i}). \end{aligned}$$

Appendix: Relationships between the roots of a polynomial solution of an ODE

In this section we give a generalized treatment for the roots of a polynomial which is a solution of an ODE. As a particular application of these results, we will obtain some identities that relate the roots of the Hermite polynomials.

We will work with the following ordinary differential equation:

$$y''(x) + a(x)y'(x) + b(x)y(x) = 0.$$

We shall assume that a possible solution for the equation will be the following N degree polynomial:

$$P_N(x) = \prod_{i=1}^N (x - x_i),$$

which we will also denote by $y \equiv P_N$. Of course, $\{x_i\}$ is the set of roots of the polynomial.

With these first concepts introduced, we define for any $j \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ the following functions:

$$y_j(x) := \prod_{i, i \neq j} (x - x_i), \quad (12)$$

$$f_j(x) := \log y_j(x) = \sum_{i, i \neq j} \log(x - x_i). \quad (13)$$

It is immediate from the definition that $y(x) = (x - x_j)y_j(x)$. Moreover, if we denote by $^{(n)}$ the n th derivative of a function (for $n = 0$ it simply refers to the original function) we have that for any non negative integer n ,

$$y^{(n)}(x_j) = ny_j^{n-1}(x_j). \quad (14)$$

Similarly, from the definition of the functions f_j we deduce that

$$f_j^{(n)}(x) = (-1)^{(n+1)}(n-1)! \sum_{i, i \neq j} \frac{1}{(x - x_i)^n}, \quad n \geq 1.$$

We will be interested in the value of these last expressions when $x = x_j$ because they will allow us to compute the following sum that relates the roots of the polynomial:

$$s_n^j := \sum_{i, i \neq j} \frac{1}{(x_j - x_i)^n} \Rightarrow s_n^j = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{f_j^{(n)}(x_j)}{(n-1)!}. \quad (15)$$

Now we need to find the expressions for $f_j^{(n)}$ in terms of the function y_j and its derivative. For these computations, it will be clearer and easier to define the following auxiliary functions for every $n \geq 0$:

$$v_n := \frac{y_j^{(n)}}{y_j}.$$

With this definition it is straightforward to check that

$$v_n' = v_{n+1} - v_n v_1.$$

From this point it is quite simple to get the expressions for the first derivatives of f_j in terms of these new functions:

$$f_j' = v_1, \quad (16)$$

$$f_j'' = v_2 - v_1^2, \quad (17)$$

$$f_j''' = v_3 - 3v_2v_1 + 2v_1^3, \quad (18)$$

$$f_j^{(4)} = v_4 - 4v_3v_1 + 12v_2v_1^2 - 3v_2^2 - 6v_4, \quad (19)$$

...

With these relations set up, if we want to obtain s_n we just need to know the value of $v_i(x_j)$ for $i = 0, \dots, n$. It is trivial that $v_0(x_j) = 1$. To get the rest of the values we will make use of the ODE in a recursive way. This process will consist of differentiating the ODE $n - 1$ times and evaluating it for $x = x_j$ to obtain $v_n(x_j)$ once we already know the values of $v_i(x_j)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n - 1$. In this document we will carry out the three first cases.

Case $n = 1$:

For this case we will just evaluate the ODE for $x = x_j$ and use the equation (14), obtaining that:

$$2y_j'(x_j) + a(x_j)y_j(x_j) = 0,$$

where we have also used that y is solution of the ODE and that $y(x_j) = 0$. Now, if we divide the expression by $y_j(x_j)$, then we have that:⁵

$$2v_1(x_j) + a(x_j)v_0(x_j) = 0,$$

and hence,

$$v_1(x_j) = -\frac{a(x_j)}{2}.$$

If we now make use of (15) and (16), then we have that

$$s_1^j = \sum_{i, i \neq j} \frac{1}{x_j - x_i} = f_j' = v_1(x_j) = -\frac{a(x_j)}{2}. \quad (20)$$

Case $n = 2$:

For this case we will start by differentiating the ODE and later evaluating it at $x = x_j$. Then, if we divide the result again by $y_j(x_j)$, we can express it in terms of v_i :

$$3v_2(x_j) + a(x_j)2v_1(x_j) + (a'(x_j) + b(x_j))v_0(x_j) = 0.$$

⁵In this step we have assumed that $x_i \neq x_j$ for each $i \neq j$ so that $y_j(x_j) \neq 0$. However, without this condition it makes no sense to talk about the sum s_n so we were actually assuming it implicitly from the beginning.

If we substitute the values for $v_0(x_j)$ and $v_1(x_j)$ that we already have, we get that

$$v_2(x_j) = \frac{a^2(x_j) - a'(x_j) - b(x_j)}{3}.$$

Therefore, if we use the equations (15) and (17) we get that

$$s_2^j = \sum_{i,i \neq j} \frac{1}{(x_j - x_i)^2} = -f_j''(x_j) = -nu_2(x_j) + v_1^2(x_j) = \frac{a'(x_j) + b(x_j)}{3} - \frac{a^2(x_j)}{12}. \quad (21)$$

Case $n = 3$:

This case is analogue to the previous one, we just need to differentiate the ODE one more time and then evaluate it at $x = x_j$. After that, if we divide it by $y_j(x_j)$ we obtain the following expression in terms of v_i :

$$4v_3(x_j) + a(x_j)3v_2(x_j) + (2a'(x_j) + b(x_j))2v_1(x_j) + (a'' + 2b'(x_j))v_0(x_j) = 0.$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} v_3(x_j) &= -\frac{3a(x_j)v_2(x_j) + 2(2a'(x_j) + b(x_j))2v_1(x_j) + (a''(x_j) + 2b'(x_j))v_0(x_j)}{4} \\ &= \frac{3a(x_j)a'(x_j) + 2a(x_j)b(x_j) - a^3(x_j) - a''(x_j) - 2b'(x_j)}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, if we use the expressions (15) and (18) we will obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} s_3^j &= \sum_{i,i \neq j} \frac{1}{(x_j - x_i)^3} = \frac{f_j'''(x_j)}{2} = \frac{v_3 - 3v_2v_1 + 2v_1^3}{2} \\ &= \frac{3a(x_j)a'(x_j) + 2a(x_j)b(x_j) - a^3(x_j) - a''(x_j) - 2b'(x_j) + 2a^3(x_j) - 2a(x_j)a'(x_j) - 2a(x_j)b(x_j) - a^3(x_j)}{8} \\ &= \frac{a(x_j)a'(x_j) - b'(x_j) - a''(x_j)}{8}. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Hermite polynomial of degree N

One particular application for these results is the case of the following differential equation

$$y''(x) - 2xy'(x) - 2Ny(x) = 0,$$

whose solution is the Hermite polynomial of degree N . Therefore, if we substitute $a(x) = -2x$ and $b(x) = 2N$ in the equations (20), (21) and (22), we will have that the

following relationships between the roots of the polynomial:

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{i,i \neq j} \frac{1}{x_j - x_i} &= x_j, \\ \sum_{i,i \neq j} \frac{1}{(x_j - x_i)^2} &= \frac{2(N-1) - x_j^2}{3}, \\ \sum_{i,i \neq j} \frac{1}{(x_j - x_i)^3} &= \frac{x_j}{2}.\end{aligned}$$

Particularly, this last expression tell us that the roots of the Hermite polynomial of degree N are a critical point of the potential (8).

ENTANGLEMENT

Introduction to entanglement and entanglement entropy

The study of many classical particles systems entails an inherent and trivial property in this context: the knowledge of the state of the whole system allows us to determine the state of each of its particle. However, this is not the case in the study of quantum system, due to the linear nature of Quantum Mechanics. For example, if we have a system of N quantum distinguishable particles, its states will be part of a Hilbert space of the form $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \dots \otimes \mathcal{H}_N$, where \mathcal{H}_i is the Hilbert space associated with the states of the i th particle. In this context, the states of the system will not only be of the type $|\psi\rangle = |\psi_1\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |\psi_N\rangle$, where we can easily spot that the i th particle is in the state $|\psi_i\rangle$, but any linear combination of these types of product states will be valid. Then, for an arbitrary state

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{j \in J} \alpha_j \cdot |\psi_{1,j}\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |\psi_{N,j}\rangle,$$

where J is a set, not necessarily finite, and $\sum_j |\alpha_j|^2 = 1$, we cannot recognize the specific state of each of the individual particles. This phenomenon is known as *entanglement*.

Once the concept of entanglement is introduced, the next question that arises is how we can quantify and measure it. To answer this question we first need to introduce the notion of density matrix (denoted by ρ), which is an operator on the Hilbert space that generalizes the concept of vector state. For a given state $|\psi\rangle$, its density matrix is simply defined as $\rho = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ and we say that the system is in a *pure state* (we know all the information about it). However, this formalism not only allows us to represent pure states, but it is also compatible with *mixed states*, where we only know the probability p_i of being in the pure state $|\psi_i\rangle$. In this case, the density matrix is $\rho = \sum_i p_i |\psi_i\rangle\langle\psi_i|$. This reformulation of the Quantum Mechanics language can be shown to be completely compatible with quantum postulates (see [7]). For example, we can compute the expected value of a measurement operator A on the state ρ as $\langle A \rangle_\rho = \text{tr}(\rho A)$, where $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ denotes the trace operator.

One of the main advantages of using density matrices is that they make the study of subsystems inside the whole system much easier. This is achieved by using the so called reduced density matrix of a subsystem. If we have a subsystem \mathcal{A} , we will be

able to write the total Hilbert space as $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B$, where B is the complement subsystem of A . Now, if we have an orthonormal basis $\{|\phi_n\rangle_B\}$ of \mathcal{H}_B , we can define the reduced density matrix of the subsystem A for a given state $|\psi\rangle$ of the total system as

$$\rho_A = \sum_n \langle \phi_n | \psi \rangle \langle \psi | \phi_n \rangle_B.$$

This is not an arbitrary definition, as it can be shown to be the only one with the following property ([7]). If we have an operator M that acts on \mathcal{H} but only affects the subsystem A , i.e., $M = M_A \otimes I_B$, where M_A is an operator acting on \mathcal{H}_A and I_B is the identity operator in \mathcal{H}_B , the following equality is always true:

$$\langle M \rangle_\psi = \text{tr}(\rho M) = \text{tr}_A(\rho_A M_A),$$

where $\text{tr}_A(\cdot)$ is the trace operator on \mathcal{H}_A .

With all of these concepts in mind, we can define the Shannon-von Neumann entanglement entropy of the subsystem as

$$S_A \equiv S(\rho_A) = -\text{tr}(\rho_A \log \rho_A) = -\sum_n p_n \log p_n$$

where $\{p_n\}$ is the spectrum of ρ_A .

In order to get some intuition on the meaning behind this definition, we first need to notice that if we diagonalize the density matrix, the value p_n tells us the probability of being in the n th eigenstate. Now, we can explore the extrema of this entropy. First, we see that if $p_n = 1$ while $p_m = 0, \forall m \neq n$ (which means that the subsystem is in a pure state), then $S_A = 0$, that is to say that we have all the information about the subsystem (the lack of information is none). On the other hand, it is an elementary optimization exercise to check that the maximum value for the entropy is reached when the probability is evenly distributed among all the possible pure states (then, of course, the total state of the subsystem is a mixed state). In this case, the lack of information about the system is maximum, as we are completely blind without any distinction between all the possible states.

Heisenberg XX model

Once the concept of entanglement entropy of a subsystem is understood, our objective will be to apply it to the study of the ground state of the Heisenberg XX model. This model consists of a chain of particles with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ with close neighbors interaction in the presence of an external magnetic field (which we will assume along the z direction).

The Hamiltonian of the system is given by the following expression:

$$H_{XX} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} (\sigma_l^x \sigma_{l+1}^x + \sigma_l^y \sigma_{l+1}^y) - \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} (\sigma_l^z - 1), \quad (23)$$

where $\sigma_l^{x_i}$ is the spin operator along the direction x_i which acts on the l th particle, $\lambda \geq 0$ is the magnetic field intensity and the particle positions are expressed modulo

N (for example, we have that $0 \equiv N$), which means that we are working with a closed chain.

Ground state of the system

In order to make the procedure for computing the ground state of the system easier, we shall relate the spin chain with a free (without spin) fermion system. To do so, we will identify a particle with spin $s_z = \frac{1}{2}$ with an empty hole in the fermion chain and a particle with $s_z = -\frac{1}{2}$ with a position that is full. This can be done by performing a Jordan-Wigner transformation (see [9] for more details about this process) using the following operators:

$$a_l = \left(\prod_{j<l} \sigma_j^z \right) \cdot \frac{\sigma_l^x + i\sigma_l^y}{2}.$$

In this way, the operators a_l and a_l^\dagger annihilate and create a fermion in the position l , respectively. Moreover, we see that they fulfill the canonical commutation relations:

$$\{a_l^\dagger, a_m\} = \delta_{lm}, \quad \{a_l, a_m\} = 0.$$

With these new operators we can rewrite (23) obtaining a new expression for the Hamiltonian:

$$H_{XX} = - \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} (a_l^\dagger a_{l+1} + a_{l+1}^\dagger a_l) + \lambda \sum_{l=0}^{N-1} a_l^\dagger a_l.$$

We observe that the chain is translation invariant (since the interaction between fermions does not depend on their position on the chain). This implies that if we define the translation operator T , that moves the particle in position n to the $n - 1$ th place in the chain, the momentum $P = -i \log T$ is conserved.

To exploit this fact in our favor, we shall define (for reasons we will see soon) the following operators:

$$b_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_l a_l \cdot e^{-i \frac{2\pi k l}{N}}, \quad (24)$$

which also fulfills the canonical commutation relations:

$$\{b_l^\dagger, b_m\} = \delta_{lm}, \quad \{b_l, b_m\} = 0.$$

We can rewrite the Hamiltonian in terms of these new operators as

$$H_{XX} = \sum_k \varepsilon_k b_k^\dagger b_k, \quad (25)$$

where $\varepsilon_k = \lambda - 2 \cos p_k$, with $p_k = \frac{2\pi k}{N} \pmod{2\pi}$ ⁶.

⁶The momentum is defined *mod* 2π because so it is the logarithm of an imaginary number (which is the operation we perform to compute it).

The reason behind this maneuver (and the apparently arbitrary definition⁷ of the operators b_k) is that we can now define a basis whose elements are simultaneously eigenstates of the momentum operator (momentum modes) and of the Hamiltonian. Such basis is defined as follows:

$$|K\rangle := b_{k_1}^\dagger \cdots b_{k_M}^\dagger |0\rangle, \quad K = (k_1, \dots, k_M), \quad 0 \leq k_1 < \dots < k_M \leq N-1,$$

where $|0\rangle$ is the empty chain state.

Now, we can define the momentum operator as $P = \sum_k p_k b_k^\dagger b_k$. Clearly, if we apply the canonical commutation relations, we have that the states of the basis that we just defined are eigenstates of this operator, with eigenvalues $P(K) = \sum_{j=1}^M p_{k_j}$ (mod 2π). However, we must check that this operator actually satisfies that $T = e^{iP}$. To do so, we first need to express an arbitrary state of the basis of momentum modes in terms of the position basis⁸ using the definition of the operators b_k^\dagger given in (24):

$$|k_1, \dots, k_M\rangle = N^{-\frac{M}{2}} \sum_{l_1, \dots, l_M=0}^{N-1} e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}(k_1 l_1 + \dots + k_M l_M)} |l_1 \dots l_M\rangle_{pos}.$$

Then, if we apply the operator e^{iP} using the fact that $P|k_1, \dots, k_M\rangle = \sum_j p_{k_j}$, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} e^{iP}|k_1, \dots, k_M\rangle &= e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}\sum_{j=1}^M k_j} |k_1, \dots, k_M\rangle \\ &= N^{-\frac{M}{2}} \sum_{l_1, \dots, l_M=0}^{N-1} e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}(k_1(l_1+1) + \dots + k_M(l_M+1))} |l_1 \dots l_M\rangle_{pos} \\ &= N^{-\frac{M}{2}} \sum_{l_1, \dots, l_M=0}^{N-1} e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}(k_1 l_1 + \dots + k_M l_M)} |l_1 - 1 \dots l_M - 1\rangle_{pos} \\ &= T|k_1, \dots, k_M\rangle, \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the periodic boundary conditions of the chain (i.e., that it is closed and therefore the position $N+1$ is the same as the position 1) to show that indeed the operator that we have defined is the momentum operator (in the sense that it is the generator of the translations).

Once we have the correct basis to work with, in order to find the ground state of the system $|GS\rangle$, we need to minimize the energy of these states, which is given by $E(K) = \sum_j \varepsilon_{k_j}$ (this comes from using the canonical commutation relations when you apply H_{XX} , as defined in (25), to the state $|K\rangle$). If $\lambda > 2$ we have that $\varepsilon_k > 0 \forall k$. Therefore, the lowest energy level is obtained when $b_k|GS\rangle = 0 \forall k$, i.e., $|GS\rangle = |0\rangle$. This situation is not really interesting for our analysis (the entanglement entropy of $|0\rangle$ is just 0 because it is a product state), so we will focus only on the case $0 \leq \lambda < 2$.⁹ For these values of λ , we can distinguish between values of k for which $\varepsilon_k > 0$,

⁷Actually these operators are obtained as a (discrete) Fourier transform of the original operators, a standard procedure to change from position to momentum space.

⁸This basis is generated by the operators a_l^\dagger . We will denote its elements as $|l_1, \dots, l_M\rangle_{pos} := a_{l_1}^\dagger \cdots a_{l_M}^\dagger |0\rangle$, with $0 \leq l_1 < \dots < l_M \leq N-1$.

⁹The case $\lambda = 2$ has a similar behavior to the situation when $\lambda > 2$. However, for this value of magnetic field, the ground state is doubly degenerate because the mode with momentum $p_0 = 0$ has 0 energy too, therefore, the total energy does not change whether this mode is excited or not. However, this situation is still quite basic from an entanglement point of view, so we will not take it into account.

whose associated mode with momentum p_k will not be occupied; and values of k for which $\varepsilon_k < 0$ and the mode with the corresponding momentum is excited in the ground state. If we define $p_c = \arccos\left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right)$, we will have that $\varepsilon_p < 0$ if $p < p_c$ or $p > 2\pi - p_c$, while $\varepsilon_p > 0$ in the other cases¹⁰. This behavior can be observed in figure 1.

FIGURE 1: Value of ε_p plotted for the case $\lambda = 1$. We can see how the energy of the modes is negative if $p < p_c$ or $p > 2\pi - p_c$.

Entanglement entropy of a block

Now that we know the states with well defined energy of the system, and, in particular, its ground state, we can start to compute the entanglement entropy of a block of L particles. Actually, due to the translation invariance of the chain, we can suppose, without loss of generality, that the block is in the position $\{0, \dots, L - 1\}$. Computing this entropy directly from the density matrix is a very computationally costly method (the order of this matrix is 2^N , which means that it grows exponentially with the number of particles), so the search of an alternative method is well justified. To address this new path we will make use of the concept of correlation matrix. In particular, if we define the matrix $A_{mn} = \langle a_m^\dagger a_n \rangle$ with $0 \leq m, n \leq L - 1$, we have that its elements can be explicitly computed and, in addition, they can be related to the reduced density matrix of the block with the following expression $A_{mn} = \text{tr}(a_m^\dagger a_n \rho_L)$, relationship that we will “invert” later on to compute the eigenvalues of ρ_L .

First, when the system is in its ground state, we have that:

$$\langle b_p^\dagger b_q \rangle = \begin{cases} \delta_{pq} & \text{si } \varepsilon_p < 0 \\ 0 & \text{si } \varepsilon_p > 0 \end{cases} .$$

This is due to the particular structure of the ground state, where any mode with energy $\varepsilon > 0$ is empty and therefore is annihilated by b_p . Moreover, the product

¹⁰Here we are assuming that p_c is not a multiple of $\frac{2\pi}{N}$. If that were the case, we would have two values of k for which $p_k = 0$ and the ground state would have degeneracy 4.

between states with different excited modes is 0 (they are part of an orthonormal basis), so this expected value is 0 when $p \neq q$.

We can compute now A_{mn} inverting the transformation (24), which means that

$a_l = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_k b_k \cdot e^{i\frac{2\pi kl}{N}}$, thus

$$\begin{aligned} A_{mn} &= \langle a_m^\dagger a_n \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{p,q=0}^{N-1} e^{i\frac{2\pi(qn-pm)}{N}} \langle b_p^\dagger b_q \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{k_c} e^{i\frac{2\pi k(n-m)}{N}} + \sum_{k=N-k_c}^{N-1} e^{i\frac{2\pi k(n-m)}{N}} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{k_c} \left(e^{i\frac{2\pi k(n-m)}{N}} + e^{-i\frac{2\pi k(n-m)}{N}} \right) - 1 \right) = \frac{2}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{k_c} \cos \left[\frac{2\pi k(n-m)}{N} \right] - \frac{1}{N}, \quad (26) \end{aligned}$$

where $k_c = \frac{N}{2\pi} \cdot [p_c]$ and $[p_c]$ denotes the integer part of p_c .

We can continue developing this expression if we understand it as the real part of a geometric complex sum (taking $l = m - n$):

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{k_c} \cos \left(\frac{2\pi kl}{N} \right) &= \text{Re} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{k_c} e^{ik\frac{2\pi l}{N}} \right] = \text{Re} \left[\frac{1 - e^{i(k_c+1)\frac{2\pi l}{N}}}{1 - e^{i\frac{2\pi l}{N}}} \right] \\ &= \text{Re} \left[\frac{\sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} (k_c + 1) \right)}{\sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} \right)} \cdot e^{i\frac{\pi l}{N} k_c} \right] = \frac{\sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} (k_c + 1) \right) \cos \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} k_c \right)}{\sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} \right)} \\ \Rightarrow A_{mn} &= \frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{\sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} (k_c + 1) \right) \cos \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} k_c \right)}{\sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} \right)} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \left(\cos^2 \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} k_c \right) + \frac{1}{2} \cot \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} \right) \sin \left(\frac{2\pi l}{N} k_c \right) - \frac{1}{2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2N} \left(\cos \left(\frac{2\pi l}{N} k_c \right) + \cot \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} \right) \sin \left(\frac{2\pi l}{N} k_c \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{\sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} (2k_c + 1) \right)}{2N \sin \left(\frac{\pi l}{N} \right)}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, in the thermodynamic limit (with fixed L , we take $N \gg 1$), the resulting expression would be:

$$A_{mn} = \frac{\sin \left[\frac{2\pi k_c(m-n)}{N} \right]}{\pi(m-n)} = \frac{\sin[p_c(m-n)]}{\pi(m-n)}. \quad (27)$$

Now that we have the expression for the matrix element A_{mn} , which is equal to $\text{tr}(a_m^\dagger a_n \rho_L)$, we can try to get the eigenvalues of ρ_L from it.

As A is a Hermitian matrix, it will exist some unitary matrix U such that $G = UAU^\dagger$ is diagonal. Therefore, if we define the operators $g_p = \sum_m \overline{u_{pm}} a_m$ (which will have a certain fermionic mode associated too), the elements of the matrix G will be of the form

$$\langle g_p^\dagger g_q \rangle = \sum_{mn} u_{pm} \overline{u_{qn}} A_{mn} = v_p \delta_{pq},$$

where $\{v_m\}$ is the set of eigenvalues of the matrix A .

Actually, it must be that $G_{pq} = \text{tr}(g_p^\dagger g_q \rho_L) = v_p \delta_{pq}$, from where we can deduce that the matrix ρ_L can be written as $\rho_L = \varrho_1 \otimes \dots \otimes \varrho_L$, where ϱ_m is the reduced density matrix of the subsystem corresponding to the fermionic mode annihilated by g_m (since ρ_L is uncorrelated when we divide the system in this way).

To find the eigenvalues of ϱ_m it is convenient to express it, together with the operators g_m and g_m^\dagger , in the matrix representations corresponding to the basis of the mode (the first vector of this basis would be the excited mode state, while the second vector would be the empty mode state). The result we get is the following:

$$g_m = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad g_m^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \varrho_m = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_m & \overline{\beta_m} \\ \beta_m & 1 - \alpha_m \end{pmatrix},$$

where we have used the properties of ϱ_m as a density matrix. Since $\langle g_m^\dagger \rangle = \text{tr}(g_m^\dagger \varrho_m) = 0$ (because $\langle a_k^\dagger \rangle = 0$), it must necessarily be $\beta_m = 0$.

Finally,

$$v_m = \text{tr}(g_m^\dagger g_m \rho_L) = \text{tr}(g_m^\dagger g_m \varrho_m) = \text{tr} \left[\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_m & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - \alpha_m \end{pmatrix} \right] = \alpha_m, \quad (28)$$

and then $\varrho_m = \begin{pmatrix} v_m & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - v_m \end{pmatrix}$.

The Shannon-von Neumann entropy is additive, so we can exploit this property to compute the total entropy of the block as:

$$S_L = \sum_{m=1}^L S(\varrho_m) = - \sum_{m=1}^L (v_m \log v_m + (1 - v_m) \log(1 - v_m)). \quad (29)$$

Entropy growth

Now that we have an expression for the block entanglement entropy, it is worth studying how this magnitude changes as a function of L and λ . To tackle this task, we will get an analytic expression for (29) in the asymptotic limit $L \rightarrow \infty$.

In order to make this process easier, we will work with the values $\mu_m = 2v_m - 1$ instead of $\{v_m\}$. From (28), we deduce that for each m , v_m is part of the diagonal of a density matrix, so it must be $0 \leq v_m \leq 1$ and, consequently, $\mu_m \in [-1, 1]$, $\forall m$. On the other hand, following from the definition of μ_m , they must be the eigenvalues of the matrix

$$\tilde{A} = 2A - I_L,$$

where A is the correlation matrix in the thermodynamic limit (which is defined by (27)) and I_L is the identity matrix of order L . If we now define the polynomial

$$g(z) = \det(\tilde{A} - z \cdot I_L),$$

its only roots will be the values μ_m .

This new matrix \tilde{A} (similarly to A and the identity matrix) is a Toeplitz matrix. This means that its elements $\tilde{A}_{i,j}$ only depend in the difference $i - j$ and hence, they take the same values in each of the descending diagonals from left to right. This will be a fundamental concept for the following computations.

Let us define the function

$$f(\epsilon, z) = -\frac{1 + \epsilon - z}{2} \log \left(\frac{1 + \epsilon - z}{2} \right) - \frac{1 + \epsilon + z}{2} \log \left(\frac{1 + \epsilon + z}{2} \right).$$

We have that $S_L = \sum_m f(0, \mu_m)$ so it would be tempting to write this entropy as

$$S_L = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_C f(0, z) \cdot \frac{g'(z)}{g(z)} dz,$$

for some closed path C that encloses the $[-1, 1]$ interval, because applying the residue theorem, the integral would be equal to the sum of the function $f(0, \cdot)$ over the roots of g , i.e, the values μ_m . Nevertheless, this result is not true in general, since the function $f(0, \cdot)$ is the sum of logarithms with singularities at -1 or 1 , so it cannot be defined in any neighbors of these points, which there is no integral path that encloses them where f is defined (and holomorphic). This problem can be fixed taking the following limit:

$$S_L = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{C_{\epsilon, \delta}} f(\epsilon, z) \cdot \frac{g'(z)}{g(z)} dz, \quad (30)$$

where the path $C_{\epsilon, \delta}$ is shown in figure 2.

FIGURE 2: Integral path $C_{\epsilon, \delta}$.

The useful property from this integral is that it can be approximately computed in the limit $L \rightarrow \infty$, exploiting the fact that the function g is the determinant of a Toeplitz matrix. This procedure is based on the Fisher-Hartwig conjecture (for this special case it is actually proven) that describes the asymptotic behavior of these determinants when the order of the matrix tends to infinity. The procedure to get the value of this integral can be found in detail in [10], and the result we get is

$$\begin{aligned} S_L &= \frac{1}{3} \log L + \frac{1}{3} \log(\sin p_c) + \frac{\log 2}{3} + \gamma_1 \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \log L + \frac{1}{6} \log \left(1 - \left(\frac{\lambda}{2} \right)^2 \right) + \frac{\log 2}{3} + \gamma_1, \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where

$$\gamma_1 = - \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{e^{-t}}{3t} + \frac{1}{t \sin^2(t/2)} - \frac{\cosh(t/2)}{2 \sinh^3(t/2)} \right) dt.$$

Analyzing expression (31) in its range of validity ($0 \geq \lambda < 2$ and $l \sin p_c \gg 1$) we see that S_L achieves its maximum at $\lambda = 0$, i.e., without the presence of a magnetic field, and it decreases as λ grows. Moreover, we see that the dominant term when $L \rightarrow \infty$ is $\frac{1}{3} \log L$, which shows that if $0 \leq \lambda < 2$ we are facing a critical model.

Generalization of the model

In this section, our objective will be to study a possible generalization of the model. A possible way to approach this possibility is by changing the intensity of the interaction between particles (until now, its value was 1 for neighboring particle and 0 in other cases) to a generic function h_{ij} that measures the interaction between particles in the i th and j th position. This way, the Hamiltonian of the model would be of the form (after applying the Jordan-Wigner transformation):

$$H = - \sum_{i,j} h_{ij} a_i^\dagger a_j,$$

where $h_{ij} = -\lambda, \forall i$.

If we want the system to remain translationally invariant, we need to demand some requirements from function h_{ij} . First, it must only depend on $|i - j|$, i.e., on the distance between particles and not on their positions in the chain. In addition, as we are working with a closed chain, the function needs to be periodic, with period N . In conclusion, we have that $h_{ij} = h(|i - j|)$, where h is an even real function (so that the Hamiltonian is self-adjoint), satisfying $h(n) = h(n + N), \forall n$.

With these conditions, we can use again the operators define on (24) and find a diagonal expression of the Hamiltonian in the basis of momentum modes:

$$\begin{aligned} H &= - \sum_{i,j} h_{ij} a_i^\dagger a_j = - \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} h(n) \cdot a_j^\dagger a_{j+n} \\ &= - \sum_j \sum_n \frac{h(n)}{N} \left(\sum_p b_p^\dagger e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{N}pj} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_q b_q e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}q(j+n)} \right) \\ &= - \sum_n h(n) \sum_{p,q} b_p^\dagger b_q e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}qn} \cdot \sum_j \frac{e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}j(q-p)}}{N} = - \sum_k b_k^\dagger b_k \sum_n h(n) e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}kn} \\ &= - \sum_k \varepsilon_k b_k^\dagger b_k, \end{aligned}$$

where $\varepsilon_k = \sum_n h(n) e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{N}kn}$, the Fourier transform of h , is the energy¹¹ associated with the mode of momentum $p_k = \frac{2\pi}{N}k \pmod{2\pi}$.

From this point on, we can implement specific functions h and analyze the model we get with similar techniques as the ones used in the past sections. With this new

¹¹Since h is an even function this energy is always a real value, as we should expect.

types of interaction, it could happen that the dispersion relationship of the energy of each mode as a function of the momentum was not the same as the one in figure 1. Then, it would be possible to have more than two values for the momentum that make 0 the energy, so it would be necessary to define more than one critical momentum. A treatment of these models, specifically one with interaction between particles at distance 1 or 2, is presented in [11].

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